

BEYOND THE LOOKING GLASS: TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES ON THE LIMITED-FACE-TO-FACE LEARNING FOR LEARNERS WITH DISABILITIES

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Beyond the Looking Glass: Teachers' Perspectives on the Limited-Face-To-Face Learning for Learners with Disabilities

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Abstract

This phenomenological study aimed to provide an in-depth understanding to answer the question of how participants described their views, and feelings and how it affected their lives in teaching learners with disability in limited face-to-face learning. The 10 SPED teachers served as the respondents of the study. Given the restricted participant pool, purposive sampling was employed. Five (5) SPED teachers for the individual in-depth interview (IDI), and five (5) for the focus group discussion (FGD) from General Santos City SPED Integrated School. The Qualitative Research Method using the validated Semi-Structured Interview Guide to gather data from the participants, and thematic analysis was applied to interpret the data. Based on the findings of the study these significant themes emerged their experiences: full of adjustment, dealing with diverse behaviour, providing guidance, showing consideration, discovering the learner's situation, and attending to learners' needs. Moreover, their coping mechanism the themes were: happy to teach, fulfilled to help learners, challenged, and exhausted. Finally, for insights the themes were privileged with educational training, employed collaboration, provided quality learning, and postered positivism. The results of the study revealed that SPED teachers were happy and enthusiastic to teach learners in the limited face-to-face learning, nevertheless, the challenges of monitoring and assessing students' learning, progress, and behavior were primary factors to address in class. Hence, SPED teachers needed coping mechanisms to with the circumstances in class.

Keywords: *guidance and counseling, learners with disabilities, limited face to face, teachers' perspectives, phenomenology, philippines*

Introduction

“The best and most beautiful things in the world cannot be seen or even touched-they must be felt with the heart.” -Helen Keller

The passage illustrates that a person's life experience cannot be assessed by tangible objects to see, feel, or touch. Amazing things have happened that can-not be seen with the eyes, felt, or touched with the hand, but must be experienced with the heart. There are unseeable and untouchable experiences in this study that deepen teachers' perspectives on the limited face-to-face learning for learners with disabilities. In the context of limited face-to-face learning, the verse indicates the virtues of love, patience, and endurance for learners with disabilities. Furthermore, the nicest and most beautiful experience in life, especially when teaching learners with disabilities, is seeing them grow and develop at their own pace and interest.

The problem started in March 2020, when the World Health Organization declared COVID-19 a global pandemic. This resulted in the closure of the country's and the world's educational systems (Winthrop, 2020). Furthermore, one developing reality as a result of the global health crisis is the need to establish plans and preparations to offer various learning modes to our learners in order to reduce the risk of face-to-face interaction. Using student self-learning modules (SLM), various platforms for online learning, and radio-based teaching for learners from rural loca-tions to be accessed through radio frequencies for their learning. Parents of learn-ers with disabilities are directly responsible for teaching the lesson at home. Par-ents acknowledged the difficulties in teaching the lesson to their children. Teachers, on the other hand, had difficulty monitoring how learners learned the lesson and completed the activity.

Also, Education was one of the industries that suffered the most during the COVID-19 pandemic at the time. As a result, UNICEF continues to emphasize the importance of establishing extra schools for in-person learning in order to help address learning gaps for learners with disabilities while transitioning to limited face-to-face schooling. Hence, the Recovering Education 2021 campaign, UNESCO, UNICEF, and the World Bank have emphasized the significance of es-tablishing more schools for in-person learning to help close learning gaps. Besides, learners feel more at ease in a school setting, and the traditional classroom setting is seen as the best component, when learners learn under the supervision of a teacher. Moreover, limited face-to-face learning is very beneficial in a student's life because interaction is a critical component of one's progress (Bisnar, 2022; De, 2021).

Furthermore, after two years of school closure and delayed schedules to prevent the spread of COVID-19 in South Africa. Students are excited to return to school, and UNICEF-supported hygiene standards are being implemented in South African schools to limit the spread of the coronavirus (Ferguson, 2022). In the Philippines, however, the government announces the resumption of classes in face-to-face learning through the Department of Education to address the problem of returning to school. Republic Act 11480 amends Section 3 of RA No. 7797. The return of the class revitalizes teachers especially when they see learners with disabilities in the classroom. Consequently, one of the most recent victories in the fight against the pandemic is the Philippine government's confirmation of face-to-face classes in low-risk areas for the virus (Abarca, 2022). In addition, despite the Covid-19 pandemic, the Department of

Education stated this year that 25,668 public schools across the country have returned to in-person learning (Inis, 2022).

Moreover, to address learning gaps caused by reduced instructional time during the pandemic, schools ought to emphasize remedial learning beginning this school year. A mental health recovery program and academic enhancement development for learners should be explored. The outcomes of the enhancement learning programs can be utilized to assess each student's numerical and literacy skills, as well as their behaviour responses in class. Finally, teachers can improve their present teaching practices and adjust them to the needs of learners (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2021).

This study aimed to find out the teachers' perspectives on the limited face-to-face learning for learners with disabilities. I focused on describing the participants' views, feelings and how it affects the lives of teachers teaching learners with disabilities in limited face-to-face learning. As a guidance facilitator, this study is beneficial for me to strengthen my capability to help and guide receiving teachers who will receive learners with disabilities for mainstreaming in the regular class-room, encourage teachers in the Special Education Department develop a positive outlook by helping and guiding learners with disabilities for greater social skills and learning development experiences in class.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to present an in-depth understanding of how participants describe their perspectives, how to cope with challenges in terms of coping mechanisms on how they feel, and how it affects their lives on the limited face-to-face learning for learners with disabilities. The intent of this research study was limited to 10 participants, who are special education teachers of General Santos City SPED Integrated school. There were 5 participants for the in-depth interview (IDI) and 5 participants for the focus group discussion (FGD). A recorder was extensively used during the in-depth interview and the written comments gathered. Different statements about their experiences and feelings they convey were grouped to form themes.

In addition, the goal of qualitative study research, particularly the phenomenological approach, is to help me to gain better knowledge and understanding of the perspective of teachers about their views, feelings, and how it affects their lives. Moreover, when researchers will read and conduct a similar study, they will be able to reflect on the teachers' perspectives, experiences, and coping mechanisms in teaching learners with disabilities in limited face-to-face learning.

Literature Review

This section presents literature related to the study under investigation. This section highlighted the literature which gave relevant and similar insights.

The Perspectives

Adaptability is something teachers require on a regular basis and likely plays an important role in helping them to navigate the demands of their work. It is found when teachers were more adaptable, they tended to report better well-being. Also, teachers must be willing to make adjustments and be flexible in order to focus on workable strategies such as direct action to control stressful situations and emotion focus strategies for learners (Adetunji, 2018). Therefore, coping flexibility is an important component of psychological resilience, which is a well-known mechanism underlying the adjustment process. Then, giving psychosocial assistance and encouragement to teachers and students in limited face-to-face learning has greatly helped recovery, primarily for learners with disabilities.

Moreover, the effective coping requires sensitivity to the various situational demands embedded in an ever-changing environment, as well as flexibility in deploying coping techniques to meet the specific needs of learners in limited face to face learning and students who attended face-to-face classes expressed satisfaction with their teachers' ability to present information excitingly and understandably, which increased student engagement (Bordeos et al., 2022). Thus, the willingness of teachers to make adjustments, preparing workable strategies for learners helped teachers face the challenges in the limited-face-to-face learning of learner with disability. Face-to-face learning ensures a better understanding and recollection of lesson content and gives class members a chance to bond with one another.

Readiness for Adjustments

The adjustments faced by teachers and students from both the of public and private schools in the country and around the world has greatly affected the educational system, and thus, the preparation and mode of learning have become one of the problems that have affected learners' learning performances in the country and around the world. Hence, as a result a new method or technique of delivering the lesson to the learners has been developed. Due to COVID-19 pandemic, teachers encountered challenges, tensions, and possibilities in the limited face-to-face classes for learners with disabilities. As observed, these difficulties and opportunities have provided teachers the opportunity to adjust and transform those challenges and dilemmas into opportunities for the growth and development of learners. The problem that took nearly two years to prepare the school system has resulted in answering the unbeatable global health problem (Ancheta & Ancheta, 2020; Gorna et al., 2021).

Thus, governments were compelled to implement drastic actions such as population reduction and the elimination of in-person training

(Ancheta & Ancheta, 2020; Gorna et al., 2021). Recognizing the difficulties of re-establishing face-to-face learning, the Department of Education stated that school opening preparations began weeks before the first day of classes. Recognizing the significance of preparing schools, teachers, and students for the return of in-class learning, the Department of Education has mandated a three-month transition period for both public and private schools (Malipot, 2022).

Adjustments include teaching material and curriculum structure, behavioral issues, lack of time, parental expectations and parental issues, motivation, self-esteem, and emotional issues. The methods used to overcome these challenges were pointed out and analysis. Each teacher was using their own methods to tackle these challenges but some methods were used generally and an individual tailored method were developed and used according to respective learners (Ahmed, 2021).

Interaction Improve Learning

Education will continue to benefit everyone, particularly the learner's life; education must continue even in the midst of a crisis like the COVID-19 epidemic. The face-to-face model of instruction emphasized the significance of interacting with teachers and learners because these interactions improved their learning through immediate feedback. The face-to-face model of instruction emphasized the significance of interacting with teachers and learners because these interactions improved their learning through immediate feedback. To better understand how students adjusted to the limited face-to-face learning environment during the COVID-19 pandemic learning must be explored. Despite the fact that the learners' return to school began with minimal face-to-face learning (Bordeos et al., 2022).

There are still possible risks caused by COVID-19, learners' education; at this point education must continue since learners may lose interest and enthusiasm for learning if education is interrupted. Learners have a tendency to forget all they learned in school throughout the years (Dayagbil et al., 2021).

Hence, face to face learning occurs when a teacher and a student meet at a predetermined location and time, typically in a school setting, for either one-on-one learning or, more commonly, group class instruction comparable to what happens in schools. In addition, teachers considered that face-to-face learning is better to online learning since learners had access to a variety of learning resources at school. It provides real-time interaction between a learner and a teacher. Learner's benefit from more interaction with others in their class (Martinez, 2022).

Furthermore, interaction promotes learning in limited face-to-face learning: Students observed that interaction in face-to-face classes promoted learning in a way that could not be accomplished by completing tasks alone. Additionally, students noticed that instructors' hands, as well as their eyes, gaze, and facial expressions, encouraged learning. Face-to-face connection encourages participation from students and conveys important social information about the lesson. More importantly, person interactions may encourage innovation and originality in the classroom (Dean, 2022).

Recovery Plan Possible

One strategy emphasized by UNESCO, UNICEF, and the World Bank in their Mission: Recovering Education 2021 campaign is the opening of new schools for in-person learning. In addition, schools can benefit from the implementation of recovery response plans to assist close learning gaps. The COVID-19 pandemic has produced tremendous economic, social, and political issues around the world. More than just a health crisis, it has resulted in an educational crisis (Dayagbil et al., 2021).

In addition, UNICEF agrees, citing studies that show that children's class-room experiences are good indicators of their "future social, emotional, and educational outcomes" (Bisnar, 2022). Teachers' preparation includes, implementing recovery approaches to motivate learners to do their best and adjust to the new environment of being able to attend school alongside classmates and teachers. Also, providing proper assessment and monitoring of learners' emotional and psychological preparation were addressed at the outset of the limited face-to-face learning.

More importantly, the integration of program on psychosocial and mental health activities for learners with disabilities for all grade levels in order to assist them prepare for academic learning and social experiences in school. We specifically show learners with disabilities how to gradually adjust to routines even before lessons begin (Dayagbil et al., 2021).

Display Positive Emotion

Teachers who work with students with cognitive, psychological, and emotional disabilities experience various emotions in their interactions with these students. Research has shown that teachers' daily emotions in student interactions can vary and develop over time. Attitudes towards students with disabilities, including those with emotional and behavioral difficulties, are generally positive among both teachers and parents. Positive teacher-student relationships lead to increased cooperation and engagement in the classroom, they also contribute to a welcoming, inclusive school climate that promotes equity, social and emotional learning, and improved student outcomes (Nishioka, 2019).

On the other hand, other teachers might say that teaching learners with special needs in limited face-to-face learning can be challenging because they have specific needs that must be met, and all of these learners should be handled fairly. In addition, the limited face-to-face learning provided advantages in the classroom: Learners will be able to concentrate harder on learning because there will be less distraction than if learning is done at home. Also, learners can gain understanding, stories and real-world examples from teachers and

other students. They have a greater chance of completing the activity and feel comfortable and learn more in a familiar classroom situation through the guidance of the teachers (Allam & Martin, 2021).

Monitor Learners Progress

The teacher also thinks that during the limited face-to-face learning, students' learning progress is slightly better than when learning from home. Students can meet directly with the teacher in class, even with limited time, which allows students to ask the teacher when experiencing problems in the lesson (Rasmitadila et al., 2022). The presence of a teacher among fellow students is different. It involves children's mental, emotional, and social well-being.

In addition, a group of people learning together can help students progress more. Teachers can engage students in activities and work directly with them. One of the options has always been collaboration with parents. Hence, communicating and sharing concerns with parents can lessen the load on instructors in the limited face-to-face time with learners who have disabilities. As a result, there is no "one size fits all" approach to special education because it is personalized to the specifications of students with disabilities (Allam, 2021; Llego, 2021).

Moreover, the implementation of learning is limited by time, direct interaction face-to-face among teachers and students and students with students is the key to achieving the learning objectives set during the limited face-to-face classes. Through interaction, the teacher can monitor the achievement of both types of students, reinforcing the form of motivation and assignments that can decrease the lag happening so far (Rasmitalida et al., 2022).

Furthermore, monitor learners progress the flipped classroom model consists of the combination of self-study activities and teacher-guided sessions. Teacher-student interaction during the guided sessions is an integral element in stimulating student learning, and it is therefore essential that teachers accurately monitor students' needs for support. Making good use of those hours is therefore important, and teacher monitoring of students is an essential component of that (Van Leeuwen, 2021).

Finally, teachers can make use of different monitoring strategies and different informational cues. As education is back to a limited face to face learning, teachers monitoring becomes evident in giving support and services to learners' needs academically, emotionally, socially. What challenges teachers experienced concerning monitoring, and how these compare to their experiences in distance learning to limited face-to-face education. Therefore, teaching learners in face-to-face learning provided teachers the data and relevant insights to teach learners with disabilities better.

Motivated to Serve

Teachers are motivated. On the part of the learners, learning motivation will not just grow without a strong will from within themselves or can grow if there is someone who stimulates them in various ways. For a teacher, examining the student's learning motivation is crucial because understanding the learning motivation of each student can increase student learning motivation. Meanwhile, for students, having the motivation to learn can increase their enthusiasm to carry out learning (Emda, 2017).

Motivation will arouse the interest of students to learn. It has the function of which is to (1) encourage students to move in order to get maximum results, and (2) as referring to carry out activities in achieving the objectives specific objectives. Also, motivation has traits include: resilient in the face of adversity, diligently not easily bored and others. Students can reach a good study achievement on him when there is motivation to learn from the teacher (Arlinda, 2022).

Thus, motivation is an impulse that exists within a person aiming to perform an action, whether done intentionally or unintentionally in order to achieve a goal. Strengthening and growing motivation to learn is in the hands of the teachers. Besides students, the most important element in learning activities is the teacher. Teachers are educators who play a role in pedagogical engineering. They develop learning designs and implement it in the teaching and learning process. Teachers also act as educators who teach values, attitudes, morals and social skills and to carry out this role a teacher is required to have broad knowledge and insight which will later be taught to learners with disabilities.

Fulfilled and Guided

Self-learning modules (SLM) and other classroom methodologies for teaching-learning are employed in the limited face-to-face learning educational setting given two and a half days per week (Inis, 2022). Teachers are delighted to see learners transition to the new learning mode; consequently, providing advice for learners with disabilities in the limited face-to-face learning is essential. As a result, learners need encouragement and assistance while they get acquainted with the classroom setting, which affects how they feel and interactions with classmates and other students.

Prepared and Supported

Teachers must be able to adapt to technological advancements in order to prepare for challenges in this age of technology. This means that schools must also ensure that teachers receive frequent and continuous learning and skill training on how to deliver learning successfully through both physical and distant means. It goes without saying that private educational institutions must begin to increase the amount they spend on digital tools that teachers must be efficient in using.

Additionally, as we slowly make our way in the new normal and toward recovery from the drastic impacts of the pandemic, there is one important lesson that schools must keep: the way to go is to embrace innovation. For schools, they can do this by cultivating an innovative mindset and by going out of their way to support students and teachers alike (Bisnar, 2022).

Sustained in Facing Challenges

There are challenges pointed out by teachers and they use their own methods to tackle these challenges however, some methods were used generally and individual tailored methods were developed and used according to respective learners. Educational development programs. Nevertheless, children with learning disabilities need extra attention in terms of curriculum adaptation, teaching methods, and availability of teaching and learning materials, assistive technology, assessment systems, as well as resources and funds for more assistance in adapting to the school environment (Asmaveedu, 2021).

Deserve Educational Support

Learners' learning experience have improved as a result of their distance learning experience; however, learners with disabilities find it difficult to learn on their own, even if their parents or another adult in the family is willing to assist in teaching the lesson to the learners. Likewise, it did not disregard the value of limited face-to-face learning in enhancing the learner's academic, mental, physical, social, and life abilities. Every child deserves equal educational opportunities, no matter their physical or intellectual ability (Covey, 2024).

Keep Focus on Learners' Situation

To address learning gaps caused by reduced instructional time during the pandemic, schools ought to emphasize remedial learning beginning this school year. A mental health recovery program and academic enhancement development for learners should be explored. The outcomes of the enhancement learning programs can be utilized to assess each student's numerical and literacy skills, as well as their behavior responses in class. In addition, teachers can improve their present teaching practices and adjust them to the needs of learners (UNESCO, 2021).

Also, the World Bank has emphasized the significance of establishing more schools for in-person learning to help close learning gaps (Bisnar, 2022). Besides, learners feel more at ease in a school setting, and the traditional classroom setting is seen as the best component, when learners learn under the supervision of a teacher (De Wet, 2020). The limited face-to-face learning is very beneficial in a student's life because interaction is a critical component of one's progress. One of the most recent victories in the fight against the pandemic is the Philippine government's confirmation of face-to-face classes in low-risk areas for the virus (Inis, 2022). Despite the Covid-19 pandemic, the Department of Education stated this year that 25,668 public schools across the country have returned to in-person learning (Studentdesk Ims, 2022).

Methodology

This section presents the research design employed in this study. This includes the role of the researcher, research participants, data collection, data analysis approach, trustworthiness, and ethical consideration.

In this study, the researcher used qualitative research in particular phenomenology. The definition of qualitative research involves collecting and analysing non-numerical data like text, video, or audio recording to understand concepts, opinions, or experiences. It can be used to gather in-depth insights into a problem or generate new ideas for research. Qualitative research collects the views, behaviours, and experiences of people. Rather than addressing how many or how much, it addresses how's and why's. It might be set up to function as a stand-alone study that only uses qualitative data.

A qualitative research method called phenomenological research aims to identify and characterize a phenomenon's fundamental elements. This method looks into what people actually experience on a daily basis. Phenomenological research examines lived events to learn more deeply about how individuals interpret such experiences. Phenomenological researchers study on the assumption that individuals process their experiences using a universal structure or essence. To understand the core of the event being studied, they interpret the participants' thoughts, feelings, and perceptions. Qualitative research is helpful for investigating people's thoughts and feelings in-depth about case studies and for individual inquiries (Tenny et al., 2022).

The research design used in phenomenology is descriptive. The researcher wants to provide an accurate description of the composition of a phenomenon. In addition, phenomenology is a form of qualitative research that focuses on the study of an individual's lived experiences within the world (Neubauer et al., 2019).

Phenomenological researchers believe that people employ a common structure or essence to make sense of their experiences. They analyse the feelings, perceptions, and beliefs of the participants in order to clarify the essence of the topic under inquiry. The researcher must support whatever prior assumptions they have about the experience or phenomenon when conducting phenomenological research.

In addition, qualitative phenomenological research is a method that investigates and comprehends the interpretations that people or groups make of a social or human issue. Because the analysis and interpretation aim to understand and describe the universal essence of a phenomenon. The approach investigates the everyday experiences of human beings while suspending the re-searchers'

preconceived assumptions about the phenomenon. In other words, phenomenological research studies lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how people understand those experiences (Delve & Limpaecher, 2022). The objectives of qualitative phenomenological research are to generate de-tailed descriptions of the phenomenon, to depict a lived experience of a spectacle and to look for reality in people's stories of their experiences and emotions (Creswell, 2018).

Furthermore, phenomenology is an inductive and reflective methodology. The phenomenological research approach entails gathering information on a person's lived experiences as they recall them. In phenomenological study, lived events and essences are a construct. As the person presents their point of view, lived experiences are used to identify the phenomenon's universal structures. People's reactions to a circumstance are expressed through lived occurrences. According to Creswell, the phenomenological approach is most suited for re-search in which it is critical to understand numerous individuals' similar or shared experiences of a topic (Creswell, 2018).

The research participants of this study were ten selected Special Education Teachers of General Santos City SPED Integrated School of General Santos City. For the inclusion criteria, there are five (5) participants for individual in-depth inter-view (IDI), and five (5) for the focus group discussion (FGD). The participants for the inclusion criteria for the individual in-depth interview (IDI) are teachers of learners with visual impairment (HI), children with autism (CWA), and children with intellectual disability (CWID). In addition, the participants for the focus group discussion (FGD) are teachers handling learners with visual impairment (VI), hearing impairment (HI), children with autism (CWA), and Children with Intellectual disability (CWID). All participants have been employed for 3 years and above in this institution. The exclusion criteria states that teachers teaching in regular classes are not included participants in the research study because the focus of the data gathering was on participants who were teaching on limited face-to-face learning for learners with disabilities.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study which consisted of the participants' data and analysis from the interview. The different themes which emerged through data analysis were presented with supporting citations from the narrative accounts that answer the stated problems. This study sought to answer the following questions: 1. How do participants describe their views on the limited face-to-face learning for learners with disabilities? 2. How do participants feel about limited face-to-face learning for learners with disabilities? 3. What are the effects of limited face-to-face learning in the lives of participants for learners with disabilities?

All participants shared that they are full of excitement for the limited face-to-face learning seeing their learners in the classroom. They are prepared for the many adjustments on transition of limited learning, being able to adjust with the emotional feelings of the learners.

In addition the preparation and the implementation of the schedule of classes by batch takes into consideration. The participants observed that learners have different needs, shared their experiences in dealing with diverse behavior of learners and provide interventions, provide guidance, showing consideration, being patient when challenges like tantrums of learners are addressed.

The participants perspective of the limited face-to-face learning after the COVID-19 pandemic were full of excitement to see learners back to school. The participants shared thoughts, aspirations and experiences in preparation of the limited face-to-face classes. The participants prepared for the adjustments like lesson preparation, class schedule according to the level by batch of learners with disabilities The participants perspective emphasize the significance of interaction (Latoja, 2022) of teachers and learners is vital because interactions improve their learning through immediate feedback (Bordoes et al., 2022). In addition, the participants can engage much easier with students and keep an eye on learners, interact, as questions, get answers straight away (Wright, 2020).

Moreover, the participants can provide better one-to-one attention for learners and lessons can be done at a time suitable for learners with disabilities in the classroom. Also, the participants expressed their desire to help learners achieved their reading, writing, and mathematical skills (Parrish, 2019). On the other hand, the participants address the different behavior of learners and implement interventions. They faced challenges but become more sensitive to the needs of learners considering the situation of the transition from pandemic to the limited face-to-face learning. Every child is unique and responds differently to education approaches, interactive environments, given time, and particular influential issues of life and culture. As a teacher, it is necessary to go beyond the formal duty call to help students in a classroom diversity setting. Also, teachers identify and address students' diverse backgrounds and natures in class, help meet their unique needs, and manage the inherent challenges (Ibiloye, 2021).

Furthermore, providing rapport with learners and allow them to express themselves can make and feel the learners feel safe and secured with teachers. Thus, the participants perspective of the limited face-to-face learning for learners with disabilities promotes is a real-life experiences of teachers providing learning despite of challenges face related to their work.

All the participants were please to return to school but they were also enthusiastic and happy to assist parents in teaching learners. They were also grateful for the school's Special Education Program assistance in preparing to return to school having a wide range of responsibilities. Students' skills must be assessed to understand their needs, and then teaching plans must be created. They must assess students' skills to understand their needs and create teaching plans. Additionally, they must organize and assign activities tailored to each student's abilities, teach and mentor students in various settings (e.g., as a class, in small groups, and individually), and write individualized education plans using parent-friendly language (Grafwallner, 2017).

In addition, All participants implemented teamwork between teachers and stakeholders, able to cooperate with other teachers just to help learners, developed teamwork and unity, able to work together with the parents, build strong bond with learners, develop an open communication with parents and build rapport with the learners. Also, the participants shared that they are fulfilled to help learners. The participants have shown the desire to help learners gives them joy and fulfilment. One of the best ways to recognize learners developing their skills and abilities is to appreciate their accomplishments.

As an act of appreciation, teachers were always ready to give rewards. This can be done by giving words of appreciation like a good job; you made it, great work, and giving a sticker star or a happy emoji face. Also, the daily accomplishments of learners with disability give fulfillment to teachers as they can see progress in learners. Teaching in limited face-to-face learning with special needs students allows for impacting the lives of children with disabilities, learning disorders, and developmental delays are significantly impacted by teachers who provide them with tools and resources tailored to their learning styles. Furthermore, special needs teachers find personal fulfillment in knowing that they are shaping a child's life in a way that will extend beyond their education (Arbor Associates, 2022).

Furthermore, seeing the need, being a special education teacher was a demanding, challenging, and rewarding job. All participants shared their experience preparing oneself physically, emotionally, and psychologically to face students with various challenges in the classroom that requires thoughtful and skilled planning. At times, the frustration that participants experienced was geared toward the outcome or accomplishments the learners would do or behave in the classroom. Teachers get tired when students are uninterested in the instruction. hence, they need more energy to work at home after offering their attention, supervision, and teaching learners for the day's lessons. There is a significant benefit for teachers to see learners accomplish the given task for the day; although teachers are exhausted, the feeling of fulfilment is of great reward. In addition, the flexibility of the activity in the limited face-to-face learning is given to learners to reinforce the lesson; thus, the idea of asynchronous learning also applies to homework (Scheiderer, 2022).

More importantly, the participants tasks, including auxiliary paperwork, IEP preparations, and meeting or unforeseen behavioral issues in the classroom contribute to general physical reactions to stress, including fatigue, body aches, and difficulty falling and staying asleep, the heavy responsibility of classroom management needed to bear more weight. However, even the most diligent teacher can be overwhelmed by paperwork. Overload leads to burnout, especially for special educators who need extra energy to facilitate learning. Designing these jobs without additional stress is essential. (Teaching Channel, 2023).

Table 2. *The Teachers' Feelings About Their Limited Face-to-Face Learning for Learners with Disabilities*

Clustered Themes	Essential Themes
Teachers are happy in doing their task They feel glad to see their learners' progress Happy to communicate with the learners when there is a problem Happy to see learners being back to school again Glad to also help the parents in teaching learners Thankful for the support of the administration Happy to give reward and commendation to the learners Grateful for the accomplishments of learners with disability	Satisfied to Teach
Felt the fulfilment of learners' great development Fulfilled to help learners understand the lesson Fulfilled to attend with the learners' need Teachers show love and appreciation to the learners Fulfilled to give learners a lot of attention and affection Fulfilled when learners can follow the given activities Felt satisfied in recognizing the potential of the learners	Fulfilled to Help Learners
Challenged with the learners' comprehension level Learners' attitude is challenging Learners' tantrums felt very challenging for teachers Challenged because some learners have severe behaviour Challenged in handling learners with different kinds of disabilities	Challenged
Teachers felt frustrated but so quiet about it Felt tired and drained They do not have energy left to work at home Felt very tired to handle learners with severe learning disability Felt tired when learners do not show interest with the lesson	Exhausted

One of the participants shared All participants unanimously prepared to get to become an advocate for the individual needs of students with disabilities. Teachers' have the opportunity to use their experience to be an ambassador as you advocate on behalf of the special needs population at large – not only in educational settings but also in your community (Arbor Associates, 2022).

One of the participants shared about the privilege of training was a great help for teachers in the workplace. The different training experiences provided opportunities for teachers' growth and professional development. Privileged with educational training really, to learn, unlearn, and re-learn gave insights and skills as well as appropriate strategies to be applied in the classroom. Furthermore, teachers who were trained became resource speakers and facilitators to other teachers to make other teachers efficient

and effective in their field of teaching. Teachers often talk about their commitment to lifelong learning. After all, teachers can be seen as lifelong students themselves. Given this, it's clear that ongoing professional development is crucial for teachers leading special education classrooms (Scispace, 2023).

Table 3. *The effects of teaching learners with disabilities in the teachers' lives during the limited face-to-face learning*

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
Teachers were able to attend seminar-workshop face-to face and online)	Privileged with Educational Training
Became speaker and facilitator in sign language training Supported by DepEd and school administration Attend training in teaching learners with disabilities Taught how to handle learners with disabilities	
Implemented teamwork between teachers and stakeholders Able to cooperate with other teachers just to help learners Developed teamwork and unity Able to work together with the parents Build strong bond with learners Teaching reinforcement was also done at home Developed an open communication with parents Build rapport with the learners	Employed Collaboration
Employed special program to attend learner's need Helped the learners grow and achieve many things Encourage learners to strive harder and improve their skills Produce quality output Teachers became more dedicated and committed Aimed for productive improvement in all aspects Teach by contextualization for the learners to fully understand	Provided Quality Learning
Employed new strategies Applied strategies that will boost learner's interest Provide activity that will fit to the learner's capacity Exposed learners with different teaching strategies Used different platforms in teaching	Improved Learning Styles
Assessed and monitor learner's progress Appreciated each learner Acknowledged what they can offer Provided reward and motivation Helped the learners to avoid tantrums Grateful of being a teacher to learners with disability	Valued the Work and Learners
Extend love and understanding Have a lot of patience despite the challenges Became more ready and offer kindness Motivated learners and inspired them Remember that patience is a virtue	Became More Patient
Kept being positive Believed that learners can develop their skills Believed on the capacity of the learners Never think of giving up on teaching Have a positive outlook with the learners' future	Fostered Positivism

Eventually, the participants experience from attending seminars and workshops is to make modifications, enhance, and develop a strategy to improved learning styles that applies to learners with disability. In addition, the participants shared that effectiveness relies so much on what the learners learn, giving help, addressing learning and behavior modification in class, and helping develop their skills and be ready for the mainstreaming program. Quality teaching of special education teachers improved through different learning styles involving several key aspects. Primarily, teachers must possess the correct perceptions and skills to teach students with special education needs (SENs). Good teaching practices for special education teachers include adapting their behavior according to the needs and characteristics of their students, offering support, clear guidelines, and positive feedback to motivate students toward learning.

Additionally, special education teachers must have a strong knowledge base and a sophisticated repertoire of instructional practices to effectively address their students' diverse needs. Overall, the learning styles of teachers provide quality education. Teachers have a vital role in catering to the diverse educational needs of students in the classroom. In particular, special education professionals are essential as they support regular classroom teachers and offer specialized educational assistance to students with specific needs (Dorta, 2017).

Additional effects in the lives of the participants as facilitators of learning for learners with disabilities in limited face-to-face learning, must possess love and patience to bring out the skills and abilities of learners in the classroom. Also the valuing of work greatly relies on responsibility and commitment. It gives value to learners despite the limitations of what they can do academically, physically, socially, and behaviorally. Teachers can testify to a fulfilled experience by helping and valuing the work of learners with disabilities in limited face-to-face learning. Students need us to show them that love is always possible (Grafwallner, 2027).

Indeed, our students want to believe they are the only ones in our class, on our caseload, or in our hearts. In particular, a small token of appreciation, a handwritten note, a quiet teacher-student lunch, or using our cell phone. Number tells student we care about them and their academics. The importance of building relationships cannot be overstressed. Doing extra mile and express love in many ways for learners with disabilities in limited face-to-face learning. Developing love and patience was a strong motivation for teachers to inspire learners in the classroom. The attitude of being ready and offering more kindness will contribute to motivating learners with disabilities in limited face-to-face learning.

Also, one of the key benefits of patience in teaching is improved student engagement and motivation. Patient teachers create a safe space where students feel comfortable expressing their thoughts and ideas. Patient teachers foster a sense of belonging and encourage active participation by actively listening and validating their students' feelings. Additionally, patient teachers understand that not all

students learn at the same pace. They take the time to provide individual-ized support and guidance, ensuring each student receives the attention needed to succeed. This personalized approach to teaching helps students feel valued and motivated to learn.

Truly, patience is a gift, a virtue, and a necessity. Our students require patience, but some require more support than others. Providing additional time for homework or a customized assessment could help address this challenge. Re-member that parents send us their most precious possessions, hoping we will be humble, supportive, and empathetic (Grafwallner, 2017).

Hence, teachers of students with learning disabilities may feel incapable of achieving their academic goals and need greater motivation. Learners may hold the belief that their abilities are innate and unchangeable, leading them to think that they cannot improve or change their capacity to learn and achieve. Many learners with disabilities need motivation to succeed in their class lessons. Again, motivation is crucial for students to experience learning that will take place to overcome academic challenges in the classroom. Some examples used are pictures, color coding, stories, games, explanations of teachers, and other examples provided to support students' learning and motivation (Ortiz, 2019). Nonetheless, all participants are motivated to kept being positive, believed that learners can develop their skills, have a positive outlook with the learners' future.

Conclusion

The researcher arrived at a recommendation based on the findings of the study. This study serves as a tool in answering questions, describing the views, feelings and effects in the lives of teachers teaching learners with disabilities in the limited face- to-face learning. It also provide information to assist the Special Education Department of the school about the views, feelings and effects in the lives of teachers in the limited face-to-face learning.

Consequently, the result of the study may offer teachers encouragement, new perspectives and understanding of their experiences during the limited face-to-face learning. It envisioned to uplift every Special Education Teacher to continue with the noble task they are doing for learners with disabilities. It may encourage them to remain strong and positive despite the challenges they encounter every day. Lastly, the findings of this study may provide support for individuals doing similar research.

In conclusion, the teachers perspectives on the limited face-to-face learning for learners with disabilities is challenging and fulfilling. The different themes that emerged from the participants' data are results of the study that promotes a real-life experience of teachers in General Santos City SPED Integrated School. The necessity of being prepared for the continuously altering conditions brought on by the ongoing transition of learning is a big challenge for the teachers and the institution.

Finally, the result of the study provides the readers, researchers, teachers, institution and guidance facilitators with satisfying and challenging results. The challenges amidst the COVID-19 pandemic and transitioning to the limited face-to-face learning is inevitable, teachers become resilient and take opportunities to improve and become efficient in responding to the noble task as teachers.

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